

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

LENIN AND THE 1919 REPUBLIC OF COUNCILS IN HUNGARY – WHY THE HUNGARIAN COMMUNE COULD NOT SURVIVE

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Abstract

Based on Vladimir Lenin's ideas the ultimate way to create the new, Marxian world order leads through a series of revolutions. As the end of the First World War brought the collapse of the empires of Central-Europe, the new communist regime of Hungary tried to follow the path of Russia, but the short-lived Republic of Councils in Hungary had to face severe external and internal threats during its 133-day-long existence.

Lenin welcomed the formation of the new government in Budapest in the spring of 1919, and sought to provide help for the Hungarian communists in their fight against the Entente armies, but due to the reality of the military situation of both Russia and Hungary it remained only a verbal support and a series of letters between the leaders.

Keywords: Lenin, Hungary, commune, Russia, revolution, Entente, war, republic of councils.

Lenin's thesis: Russia should only be the spark

Lenin – based on Karl Marx's writings – described the general idea of the revolution as something universal. Something that cannot be put into frames of empires or nations and their states. The idea that Russia could go alone was the furthest thing from Lenin's mind. The Marxian idea of a „world revolution” in Lenin's thinking first meant the „revolutionalization” in/of Russia – something that could give the international revolution the „initial push”.

In his works and speeches given to the Russian proletariat Lenin made several references describing the social-, economic- and political situation of Hungary and the Hungarian working class. For him it seemed to be that a capitalist way out of the crisis was not possible in relation to the Hungarian Soviet Republic, however he regarded the events of 1919 in Hungary with „historical optimism”. The main reason for that was that the proletarian revolution had also been carried out in a more developed sub-region of Europe – in comparison to Russia –, which could have served as a link to the western part of the continent promoting the goal of their ideas. Lenin defined Hungary's position in the Eastern European region as being between Germany and Austria on the one hand, and Russia and the Balkans on the other, distinguishing between different historical times and spaces. The higher economic and cultural level of the Hungarian development than that of Russia particularly captured his imagination, and fuelled his ideas about the development of socialism in Europe. For a long time Hungary was situated within a multiethnic empire, it meant in fact a relatively more developed, but still dependent country. But, he assumed, socialism as a thought and practical idea would thus find more fertile ground in Hungary than in Russia.[1]

It was precisely this „more civilised development” that Lenin often repeated, that Hungary would need less violence; „Other countries will reach the same Soviet power by other, more humane means. That is why the example of Hungary will be of decisive importance.”[2]

Hungary also proved to Lenin that the proletarian revolution was not a Russian specificum. This fact led him again and again to perceive the historical character of the Hungarian situation as different from that of Russia.

According to a newspaper report of 17th April 1919, he said in his speech that „...the Hungarian revolution may play a greater role in history than the Russian. In this cultured country, all the experiences of the Russian Revolution are taken into account...” In the same text he adds: „in terms of organisation, the Hungarian proletariat seems to have surpassed us”.[3] In this context, also in the document „Greetings to the Hungarian Workers”, he points out that in the case of Hungary, the unification of the different socialist tendencies had been achieved „in one fell swoop”, because there an anti-capitalist national unity was able to be placed on a broader basis in the war against the Entente.[4]

Therefore in April 1919 Lenin could have imagined that if in Hungary a spark of the revolution found fuel within the society it could be brought into other parts of Europe as well.

The revolution becomes international

Before and during the First World War Hungary was an intergral part of the Austro-Hungarian Empire, a dual-monarchy. After its collapse in the mid of the turmoil of the last year of the First World War, a six-month long period of political- and social revolutions began in the country. On the 30th October 1918 the Aster Revolution turned Hungary from a kingdom to a republic and opened up a totally new chapter of its history.[5]

On 13th November King Charles IV issued a declaration recognizing Hungary's right to determine the form of the state and withdrew from Hungarian affairs of state,[6] then Mihály Károlyi's provisional government proclaimed the Hungarian People's Republic on 16th November 1918. Based on pacifist ideas he ordered the full disarmament of the army and due to this, Hungary was to remain without a national defence at a time of particular vulnerability. The self-disarmament made

the occupation of Hungary directly possible for the armies of Romania, the Franco-Serbian army of the Entente and the armed forces of the newly established Czechoslovakia.

The government of Károlyi resigned due to the Vix Note from the Entente that established a demarcation line between the Romanian and Hungarian armies after Romania rejoined the war – now against Hungary – and made decisive advances. The 21st March 1919 meant the end of the first Republic and the proclamation of the Republic of Councils in Budapest. The second socialist state in the world ever to be formed, preceded only by Soviet Russia, yet controlling only about 23% of the territory of pre-war Hungary of 325 411 km².

Though the de jure leader of the Hungarian Soviet Republic was president Sándor Garbai, the de facto power was in the hands of foreign minister Béla Kun, who maintained constant and direct contact with Lenin.

He welcomed the formation of the new government – partly as he knew Kun well personally. His interpretation on the seizure of power in March was based on the heroic concept that at great peril, the Károlyi-government – what he called the „Kerensky fraction of Hungary” – voluntarily invited the communists (out of the prison) to govern.[7] However the reality of the events were not exactly like this, the tendency that helped the communist government reach the power was large-scale, visible and tangible.

The end of the war also meant the „revolution of the national idea” – especially in the East-Central European region as it resulted in the birth of several new or ‘old-new’ states. Lenin’s assumption was that if during the national wars the nationalism and the social aspirations would be intertwined the chances of victory for the revolutions were multiplied. This idea was proved wrong, though at a certain time it seemed to be possible.

The end of the War had serious effects on the way of thinking and on the belief of masses of people. The post-war collapse and trauma hit the whole societies of all belligerent countries hard enough to start questioning the bases. It was an „unprecedented historical situation that compelled the citizens of Hungary – the proletariat, the landless peasants, tens of thousands of students, artists, intellectuals, displaced war veterans, many members of the bourgeoisie and even segments of the aristocracy, and nobility – to try something they had never tried before: they agreed that their only defense against [the total anarchy of the collapse] was [socialism-communism]. This was, in short, a natural reaction by people who are pushed to the brink.”[8]

The barrier to success: military aspects

To answer the question why the Revolution could not spread beneath the borders of Soviet Russia, why it stopped and could not find a stable base in Western parts of the continent, the main point lies in the military situation of the time – and to analyze it, both the Hungarian and the Russian scenes need to be observed.

The key argument is that Lenin had the idea to help stabilize the situation and the base of the Hungarian Soviet regime. In a letter he wrote to Béla Kun only one day after the new government formed, he assured Kun

that „*the working class of Russia will come to their aid with all its might*” and „*...will not allow the imperialists to lay their hands on the new council.*”[9] The only possible and useful way would have been through military assistance, but the reality emerged as an insurmountable barrier to success.

At the time of the proclamation of the Republic of Councils of Hungary there were several frontlines lying on the country’s (former) territory with both active and passive fights going on. On 21st March 1919 the Hungarian Eastern front held against the Royal Romanian Army was at around the ranges of Bihar mountains – a line stretching south from river Maros to the Northeastern Carpathians in the north. This roughly signed the historical border territory of Transylvania – fully part of Romania nowadays. The Vix Note of the Entente established a demilitarized zone around the current borders of the two countries in late March. During the spring of 1919 the Red Army of Hungary was the only power to fight for the territorial integrity of the country – besides a special corps named „Székely Hadosztály” led by conservative former WWI generals – however, they only reached partial success and have laid down the arms in late April.[10]

In mid April the Red Army tried to execute an interventional attack on the Romanian Army that led to a fast defeat – causing the retreat of the Reds into the core areas of the country and the advance of the Romanian Army to river Tisza – deep inside the territory of current-day Hungary.

In the south the line along river Maros continued westwards reaching river Dráva – south of it was the Entente Army led by French general Louis Franchet d’Esperey along with the Royal Serbian Army that marched up until this line after the Belgrade treaty – an armistice treaty that marked the southern demarcation line between Hungary and the Kingdom of Serbia.

The third – and last – frontline was in the north held by the Czechoslovak army with a line in the end of March roughly around the current Hungarian-Slovak border. In late April the Czechoslovak troops also crossed the northern demarcation line, and in a few days they occupied big parts of the northern areas of the country – resulting in the Czechoslovak and Romanian armies meeting by river Tisza.

Even though forming a corridor in geographical sense was getting to be impossible as the events of wars were going on, a short-lived chance kept the hopes alive until the mid of the summer. The Hungarian Red Army has succeeded in advancing towards the ranges of the Northeastern Carpathians, and on the (re)conquered territories it gave help in organizing the Slovak Republic of Councils. It was supposed to create a meeting point with the Soviet Red Army during the summer, however both because of the manipulation of the Entente[12] and of the military situation over the Carpathians could not happen.

Meanwhile the military situation in Russia was different in some aspects, but still struggling from the perspective of the Russian Red Army and Lenin. The main similarity was the constant fight and the wars going on all sides. In March 1919 the Russian Civil War

was in a phase when the White Army made decisive advances on the Eastern/Siberian front. Even though earlier the Red Army captured Kiev on 3rd February, Anton Denikin's military strength continued to grow in 1919 with significant munitions supplied by the British. Therefore, by the time of the proclamation of the Soviet Republic in Hungary the Red Army of Russia was surrounded by White, British, French and Polish forces on all sides if we look at the map.

The Soviet-Polish War which started at the beginning of the year 1919 meant another big obstacle to reach success – not only in relation to Soviet Hungary, but in general. In early March the Polish forces made advances deep into Soviet-controlled Lithuanian territories; they captured Vilnius on the 19th April with the leadership of Marshal Józef Piłsudski.[12]

Some days later Lenin ordered the Western Front leadership to reclaim the city as soon as possible, but the Red Army was defeated. The disability to accomplish the objectives made the Red Army change the focus – therefore from May on the key fights were the ones on the Southern Front in Volhynia, Galicia and Podolia – as well as the war with the Russian Whites that was still going on.

During the spring of 1919 when not only all but any help provided by Soviet Russia, that could have been vital for the survival of Soviet Hungary, was not possible. The path to Hungary was completely blocked in a geographical sense because of the constant military situation. The second factor was the Civil War, the war with the Whites. These two hostilities that were both situated in the heart of Russian land let no other choice for Lenin but just to fight for its own existence and to leave Hungary fight its part of their common war alone.

The expectation of Hungary to have the help of Soviet Russia against its Entente-backed neighbours was proved wrong. Lenin was officially informed on 22nd March 1919 that Soviet Hungary offered a defensive-offensive alliance – but he only sent his greetings back and left the proposal unanswered.[13] He was not able to have the Red Army to be sent to the Carpathians to unite with the Hungarian Soviets – even though Leon Trotsky favoured the idea. Lenin's idea was to split the armies as in March 1919 he needed advance both in Ukraine and in Siberia.

In mid April Béla Kun reported to the Revolutionary Governing Council that he had sent messages to Lenin asking them when the two Red Armies would be unified on one front, and proposing an incursion from the Russian Red Army into Transylvania at Máramaros.

Several more messages were sent from Béla Kun to Lenin during April and May – some written in a pleading, some in an angry way, however they were not answered.[14] After the fall of the council system in early August 1919 – due to the Romanian occupation of Budapest – Lenin while giving a speech at a workers's conference simplifies the reason for defeat to the public saying „*we have been and will be saved by this vast territory, but Hungary is too small to repel all its enemies.*”[15] In reality he considered the conquest of the Ukrainian Donetsk Basin more important than the plan of linking the Russian Red Army with the Hungar-

ian one through Romania or Poland – he was preoccupied with the Russian revolution at the expense of world revolution.

Conclusion

The revolution in Russia was not only a movement against the political system of the time, but it brought a movement against the revolution that was first realized in military conflicts because of the geopolitical reality of the post-World War situation. It had its impact on the era both in political-, social-, economic- and cultural ways.

The greatest realization of the story of 1919 is also that during the spring of 1919 the ideas had to face the reality and the possibilities, and only through this way the actual realization could have happened. The result turned to be unsuccessful from the perspective of the Russian and the Hungarian communist elites. That time was a special occasion for the revolution to spread, but it faced insuperable obstacles and – except in Russia – the reality won over the ideas by the end of the summer 1919 in Central Europe.

It seems clear that Lenin, on the one hand, intellectually, theoretically and politically, prepared the new wave of revolutions, welcomed the initiatives and supported them with what he and Soviet Russia had to offer at the time and in given and fixed circumstances. On the other hand, he undoubtedly over-estimated the depth of this revolution, its universal maturity, the vulnerability of the capitalist system of the „Wallersteinian Centre” and its weaknesses in its capacity for integration – and the ‘will’ for a world revolution proved to be a historical exaggeration at the time.

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